

SCHOOL UNIFORM IN MODERN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

Over the past few years, the Ministry of Education has been increasingly raising the issue of introducing uniform school uniforms in Uzbekistan. The advantage of introducing a single standard of clothing for students by educational institutions will highlight this material.

Key words: school uniforms, school, students, discipline.

Introduction

Preparing a child for school is usually one of the most hectic periods of their life for parents in the summer. This is due not only to the need to purchase new textbooks and stationary. Of more serious concern is the acquisition of a school uniform, in which their child will have to spend a significant part of their working time. Many parents today believe that wearing the same things leads to a leveling of the personality, equalization of the creative and intellectual abilities of children, and does not contribute to the formation of individuality. But in fact, the uniform has much more pluses than minuses. Remember at least yourself if you happened to wear school suits or dresses?. Did you feel uncomfortable in them?. Rather on the contrary: no one had the opportunity to put themselves above those around them at the expense of more fashionable clothes. What mattered was only the human personality, individual abilities, that is just what should distinguish the student from the crowd. You should explain to your child that it is enough to buy expensive clothes, but this will not make him smarter, more experienced and will not add to his authority in the class. Such upbringing will surely give positive results in the future, your child will learn to strive for achievements through the use of his own knowledge.

METHODS

The main important point when wearing a school uniform is discipline. Such clothes create the right attitude to study. Even just going to school, the child is already mentally preparing for the fact that now he will have to work and in the lesson there will probably be less conversations and notes about who is dressed today.

School clothes show the child that he has a certain niche and tasks in society, just like uniformed doctors, policeman, firefighters. So that you should buy a school uniform for the class and teach the children that it is an important element of the educational process. In any case, it is important for adults to teach the children to compromise and at the same time not sacrifice their own sense of comfort. Some of the benefits of wearing a child's uniform can be highlighted Belonging to a "home" or institution, demonstrated through clothing, emblems, or colors, is synonymous with pride, prestige, and belonging to something greater. Practicality for parents whose children wear school uniforms, life can be much calmer. This is because they don't have to worry about buying all kinds of clothes for school. Teachers and students in school uniform. Moreover, in many cases, younger siblings inherit the form of their older siblings. This saves parents a lot of money and time. Another advantage of the school uniform is that it stays the same all year round, so there is no need to buy a new uniform.

England was the first country to make it compulsory to wear a school uniform. It was there that in 1552, special clothing was introduced in a London educational institution for orphans and children from poor families called Christ's Hospital. It was blue in color, as it was believed that it was this shade that would make the students more submissive. In addition, in those days, cloth of this shade was the cheapest.

The tradition of wearing a school uniform was gradually adopted by all countries that were part of the British Empire, but in Europe it did not take root too much. So, in France, special clothes for schoolchildren existed only from 1927 to 1968, and in Poland until 1988. In Japan, the form originated at the end of the 19th century and is used today. Special clothing for schoolchildren in Russia was introduced in 1834 by decree of Nicholas I. For a long time it resembled military clothing. As soon as education in Russia became available for girls, school outfits for them began to appear. Before the revolution, only members of wealthy families could get an education, so the uniform served as a sign of material well-being and belonging to high society.

DISCUSSION

In 1998, a scientific study was conducted that students in schools introduced uniforms study slightly better than those in whose schools they are allowed to walk in anything. Experts are sure that the fact is that children are not distracted by the

discussion of clothes, the uniform sets them up for more serious behavior within the walls of the educational institution and reduces the time that the child spends deciding what to wear to class today. And of course, experts think, he spends this saved time doing his homework.

Other experts laugh at these arguments and are sure that the data on the so-called improvement in academic performance is so small that it is comparable to the statistical error. In addition, it is impossible to compare performance in two public schools on the basis that one has uniforms and the other does not. Hundreds of factors affect academic performance (primarily the qualifications of teachers), so it is impossible to understand exactly how much uniforms help students. And the time saved by not having to choose what to wear, the child will rather spend on computer games, and not on lessons, not to mention the fact that it takes no more 10-15 minutes a day to choose clothes.

But most importantly, teachers in schools with compulsory uniforms spend a huge amount of time trying to control the wearing of this very form. All this translates into minutes and hours of constant remarks, nagging and discussions about the length of socks, the right shoes and the degree of ironing of a shirt, which could be spent on learning something useful from algebra. So it turns out that with the increase in time for maintaining discipline, the time for direct study is reduced. Not to mention the fact that endless arguments with teachers about the uniform (if the child does not like to wear it) become another field in which he tries to resist the system, fights with it, which ultimately worsens overall discipline, and does not improve it. As for the feeling of community with other students, it turns from a positive factor into a negative one as soon as the child leaves school: on the street, children from other schools can determine which school he goes to by the form and start bullying.

CONCLUSION

In my research work, I learned a lot about when the school uniform appeared, what was the need for its introduction. I collected material about the history of school uniforms. In the course of this work, I became convinced of the need to introduce a school uniform. After all, it is not in vain that it has existed for a long time and is very relevant. Of course, it has flaws, but still, as the results show, the parents and children themselves, for the most part, personally do not mind the school uniform.

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